

Modern Methods of Developing Wholesale Trade in Agricultural Products

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Abstract:

Deep structural changes in the economy of Uzbekistan are also taking place in agriculture. Agrological complexes are being built for the cultivation, processing of agricultural products and the formation of a wholesale market. Such agrologistic complexes ensure the modern development of wholesale trade in agricultural products. The article covers the development of wholesale trade in agricultural products. Some approaches to modern methods of organizing the wholesale of agricultural products have been absorbed before.

Keywords: wholesale, agrologistics, agropolis, wholesale-distribution centers, wholesale market, pull, food security,

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Accepted 10 January 2022
Published 14 January 2022
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5850193

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Introduction

The implementation of profound structural changes and diversification in the economy of Uzbekistan leads to the focus on the production of local raw materials in the regions, increasing the volume of production, expanding the range of finished products at enterprises. This, in turn, increases the volume of work related to the sale of finished products in domestic and foreign markets.

Today, the issues of offering, supplying and storing products in the markets are becoming more urgent. In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev in his address to the Oliy Majlis, during his visit to each region to identify changes in the regions, socio-economic development programs, to get acquainted with the life of the population, sets important tasks. In particular, among the programmatic and targeted tasks to be implemented in the economy in 2020 and beyond, the production of competitive products, finding new international markets and increasing exports, full use of transit potential, the establishment of free trade zones, regulation of domestic and foreign trade development of draft laws, development of the transport and logistics sector in the supply of our domestic products to domestic and foreign markets.

In particular, the tasks of increasing the volume of agricultural production, their deep processing and development of exports are urgent issues.

Analysis of the relevant literature

An analysis of the literature on the subject shows that in recent years, extensive research has been conducted around the world on modern methods of developing wholesale trade in agricultural products. In particular, supply chain management, marketing, finance issues in the agro-industrial complex were discussed by Van der Vorst, J.G.A.J., C. Da Silva and J.H. Studied by Trienekens (2007) [8]. Issues of improving logistics capacity under quality control in the agricultural supply chain have been studied by Van der Vorst, J. G. A. J., Van Kooten, O. and Luning, P. (2011) [9].

Scientists and experts from the CIS countries have also conducted significant research on the development of wholesale trade in agricultural products. Russian experts Magomedov A-N.D., Babkov MA, Gasanova HN have shown in their research work the development of wholesale trade in the system of agricultural products: raw materials and food [2].

Mashmedov, A-N.D., Smirnov, AA. He studied the infrastructure of food wholesale in megacities [3].

Belarusian experts Z.M. In their research, Ilina et al explored the theoretical, methodological, and practical aspects of marketing and sales in the field of agricultural products and their processing [1].

Leading Russian expert scientist Golikov E.A. In his long-term research, he noted the issues of wholesale trade, its organization, the organization of wholesale trade in agricultural products [2].

Based on the above research, current trends in the development of wholesale trade in agricultural products will be studied.

Research methodology

Monographic observation, abstract-logical thinking, scientific observation, synthesis, induction and deduction methods were used to cover modern trends in the development of wholesale trade in agricultural products.

Analysis and results

The number of wholesale enterprises and firms in the Republic of Uzbekistan has been growing rapidly over the past 2-3 years. As of July 1, 2020, the number of wholesale enterprises and organizations, excluding the sale of cars and motorcycles, amounted to 33,413. In 2020, the wholesale turnover of wholesale trade enterprises and organizations of Uzbekistan will reach 112639.6 billion soums. soums, the growth rate compared to 2019 increased by 106.2%. In some regions of the country, the wholesale trade turnover has grown sharply over the past 2-3 years. In particular, the establishment of free economic zones and small industrial zones in Navoi, Jizzakh and Khorezm regions has a positive impact on the development of wholesale trade. However, the share of wholesale trade in the economy of our country is much lower than the number of wholesale companies, organizational structures, wholesale turnover of developed countries. Wholesale trade, which is an important sector of the economy, has great potential for further development in our country. In particular, the implementation of deep restructuring and diversification of industry in key economic sectors identified in the Action Strategy for the further development of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, the development of high value-added finished products based on high-tech processing industries, especially local raw materials The tasks of accelerated development of production, development of promising sectors of the economy aimed at a high level of localization of export-oriented products are also directly related to wholesale and intermediary activities.

In addition, the volume of cultivation and processing of agricultural products in Uzbekistan is growing rapidly. This raises the issue of developing wholesale trade in agricultural products.

There is an increase in the volume of agricultural production, but there are a number of problems in organizing their sales. Problems related to the wholesale and distribution system of agricultural products are especially relevant.

There are a number of disruptions in the agricultural distribution system. The main reasons for this are:

- agricultural producers do not clearly study the needs of the market (product range, range, demand, market capacity, stocks);
- There is no wholesale infrastructure that meets modern requirements for agricultural producers;
- ineffectiveness of the quality control system in the sale of agricultural products;
- high level of product destruction, low level of marketability;
- Difficulties for farmers, small and medium-sized agricultural producers in entering the market;
- 60-80% of the value of agricultural products falls on the wholesale sector. This is 1.5-2 times more than in developed European and Asian countries, where agricultural production and trade are developed.

Due to these problems in the wholesale and distribution system of agricultural products, special attention is paid to the rapid development of agrologistics complex in Uzbekistan. Agrologistics - combines the activities of market entities engaged in the cultivation, storage, processing, packaging, loading, transportation, organization of wholesale trade and delivery to the final consumer of agricultural products.

Development of agrologistics will increase the efficiency of management of all processes in the Republic of Uzbekistan from storage, transportation and delivery of agricultural products to the final consumer. Agrologistics integrates agricultural market participants with all other areas through marketing and logistics: planning, sales, cost control, storage and transportation of finished products and materials, as well as information on the delivery of goods from the place of production to the consumer .

One of the most important objects of agro-logistics infrastructure are wholesale and distribution centers. Wholesale and distribution centers sell agricultural products to domestic and foreign markets, export, sell and supply to retail sectors.

Wholesale and distribution centers carry out operations such as placement of processed agricultural products, wet fruits and vegetables in containers, packaging, marking, preparation for transportation. It also ensures the entry of agricultural products into the consumer market. Wholesale and distribution centers serve as a link between other facilities of the agro-logistics complex: agro-logistics centers, agro-industrial park, production and logistics centers with the consumer market. The role of wholesale and distribution centers in agrology is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Composition of wholesale and distribution centers

Agricultural producers receive information about the specific needs of customers (product-quality-price-batch volume-delivery) through sales channels through the wholesale link.

Modern methods of developing the wholesale trade of agricultural products are realized through the organization of agrological complexes.

Conclusions and suggestions

1. Expansion of the activities of the Association "Uzbekozikovkatzakhira" in the preparation of stocks of agricultural products and further development of wholesale trade to ensure food security. For this purpose, division into Uzbekmevasabzavotzakhira and Uzbekozikovkatzakhira associations. "Uzbekmevasabzavotzakhira" Association with the preparation, storage, increase of refrigerated capacity of fruit and vegetable stocks, organization of delivery of fruits and vegetables to processing and retail enterprises, "Uzbekozikovkatzakhira" with all other important food stocks, their storage and sale association should be established. Establishment of specialized branches of these associations based on the capabilities of each region, district and city of the country.

2. Establishment of wholesale and distribution centers in agro-logistics complexes. Develop a mechanism to attract wholesale entrepreneurs to wholesale and distribution centers. It is expedient to establish cooperation of agro-logistics complexes with the association "Uzbekozikovkatzakhira", entrepreneurs engaged in wholesale trade.

3. In order to increase the number of wholesale entities engaged in the sale of finished products (consumer market) on an intermediary basis, it is expedient to establish the Association of "Intermediary Enterprises" under the Republican Commodity Exchange. This will lead to an increase in the number of

entrepreneurs engaged in brokerage activities, the development of the form of wholesale brokerage.

4. Establishment of agro-cities in the largest agricultural and agro-industrial regions of Uzbekistan. Agropolis includes several trade pavilions, cross-docks for wholesale (hundreds of parking spaces), various warehouses, all types of services for the population and businesses (logistics and transport, banking, consumer services, hotel services, restaurant services) should be.

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Cite this article:

Author(s), Diyor Kholmamatov Haqberdievich, (2022). "Modern Methods of Developing Wholesale Trade in Agricultural Products", **Name of the Journal:** Commonwealth Journal of Academic Research, (CJAR.EU), P, 8- 15. DOI:

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5850193> , Issue: 1, Vol.: 3, Article: 2, Month: January, Year: 2022. Retrieved from <https://www.cjar.eu/all-issues/>

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